

Analysis of the data for the d_4 coefficient

In paper [1], we established the following exact relations between the d_4 values in six lowest electronic states of CO, see Eqs. (29) and (30),

$$d_4^{1\Sigma^+} = -\frac{3}{2}\gamma + 5\delta, \quad d_4^{2\Sigma^+} = 0, \quad d_4^{\Sigma^-} = d_4^{\Delta} = \frac{3}{2}\gamma + \delta, \quad (29)$$

$$d_4^{1\Pi} = -\frac{3}{4}\gamma - \frac{1}{2}\delta, \quad d_4^{2\Pi} = -\frac{3}{4}\gamma - \frac{7}{2}\delta. \quad (30)$$

These equations express five non-vanishing constants d_4 in terms of only two parameters, γ and δ .

In paper [1], we also performed *ab initio* calculations of the DMF, $d(r_i)$, at large distances, $r_i = 4\text{-}20$ Å. For a given r_i , parameters γ and δ could be calculated in multiple ways by replacing d_4 in Eqs. (29) and (30) with $d(r_i)r_i^4$. The results of such calculations gave the values of γ_i and δ_i shown in Fig. S1. For perfectly precise *ab initio* data, the plots would be horizontal straight lines, but the data had scatter due to intrinsic errors. Therefore, for a more precise determination of d_4 , we selected the interval of $r_i = 8\text{-}16$ Å where this condition is approximately fulfilled as seen in Fig. S1. Then we used the *ab initio* points only within this interval to determine d_4 . The product $d(r_i)r_i^4$ was nearly independent of r_i , so that d_4 was determined for all five states by fitting this product to a constant. The results are presented in Table 3 of Ref. [1].

Figure S1. Parameters γ and δ as functions of r calculated by Eqs. (29) and (30) using the ACPF data. Five equations for two unknowns could be solved by multiple ways producing the plots shown.

The above fittings were performed individually for each of the five states and for each of the two *ab initio* methods/two basis sets used, i.e. 20 values of d_4 were obtained. In these **individual fittings**, Eqs. (29) and (30) have not yet been taken into account.

The next step made in Ref. [1] was to use Eqs. (29) and (30) in the fitting, i.e. to perform the **multi-curve fitting**. The data for all five states were fitted simultaneously using γ and δ as variable parameters. In other words, only two adjustable parameters were used to obtain the values of five d_4 coefficients. The results for each of two datasets obtained with the ACPF and MRCI methods are shown in Tables 3 and 4 of Ref. [1]. We reproduce them in the present Table S1, column 1.

Finally, we perform the so-called **global fitting**. Namely, the data for all five states obtained with the ACPF and MRCI methods (a total of ten datasets) were fitted simultaneously with use of Eqs. (29) and (30), considering γ and δ as adjustable parameters, and the uncertainties were assigned to each data point as the differences between the ACPF and MRCI values. Thus, only two adjustable parameters instead of ten were used to fit the above ten datasets.

The fitted parameters are shown in column 2 of Table S1, where the error limits are standard deviations of the fit. For the ground state, we can safely take the value of $d_4 = -5.1 \pm 0.1$ used in the main text. The error indicated is much smaller than the intrinsic uncertainty of the *ab initio* data as manifested in the large difference of 0.49 between the figures in column 1. This is the consequence of the restrictions imposed by Eqs. (29) and (30). Since in the excited states the differences are only 0.10, 0.05, 0.14, and 0.10, respectively, the possible uncertainty in the ground state is greatly reduced.

The above value of $d_4 = -5.1$ is also supported by the following calculation. As explained in the main text, Sec. 2.2 (*Ab initio* calculation of the DMF), there are significant difficulties in the calculations of the DMF at large distances by the ACPF method that have been overcome in the present study. Fitting the new $d(r_i)r_i^4$ data gave the value of $d_4 = -5.1$ that differed significantly from the value of -5.40 obtained in Ref. [1].

Table S1. The values of d_4 , γ and δ (all in $\text{D}\text{\AA}^4$) calculated by **the multi-curve** (col 1) and **global** (col 2) **fittings**.

	ACPF/MRCI	Global fitting
	1	2
$1\Sigma^+$	-5.40/-4.91	-5.08±0.04
Σ^-	+5.56/+5.46	+5.50±0.01
1Π	-2.78/-2.73	-2.75±0.01
2Π	-2.86/-3.00	-2.96±0.01
Δ	+5.56/+5.46	+5.50±0.01
γ	3.687/3.576	3.620±0.003
δ	0.026/0.092	0.070±0.002

References

1. Ushakov, V.G., et al., *Long-range potentials and dipole moments of the CO electronic states converging to the ground dissociation limit*. Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys., 2020. **22**: p. 12058-12067.